

**ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL SITUATION AND FOREIGN
RELATIONS OF BUKHARA REGION (1991-2021)**

TUYEV FAZLIDDIN ERKINOVICH

Lecturer of Pedagogical Institute of Bukhara State University

Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Annotation: this article discusses and analyzes the economic and social situation and Foreign Relations of Bukhara region (1991-2021) and changes and innovations in Bukhara.

Keywords: Bukhara region, social economic potential, foreign countries, Foreign Relations.

In 1992-1994, a number of works on economic development were carried out in Bukhara region. The construction of the Bukhara Oil Refinery, which is of republican importance, determined the prospects of the Qarovulbazar district. Work worth 6 billion soums was completed here in three months. By the end of the year, a number of works worth 8 billion soums were completed in the construction of the plant. The plant is planned to have the capacity to process 5 million tons of oil per year, and it is planned to provide employment to 3,000 people.

Despite the disintegration of the former Union and the severing of economic relations, the industrialists of Bukhara region managed to increase the volume of production every month. Until December 1993, (in eleven months) the rate of production growth was 104.2 percent compared to the same period of the previous year. About 58 billion soums worth of industrial products were produced, 2.3 billion soums more than the previous year. In particular, 32.0 percent growth rates were achieved in machine building, 30 percent in local industry, 21 percent in bread production enterprises, and 9 percent in light industry.

The production volume of consumer goods increased by 95.2 billion soums, i.e. by 8.0%. Of course, industrialists did not achieve this on their own. Such achievements were achieved due to the introduction of modern technologies to the network, total reconstruction of workshops.

In particular, in the Bukhara thread production association, modern equipment imported from Germany and Switzerland was installed, as a result, the enterprise was able to produce yarn meeting world standards.

A new technology has been introduced at the Bukhara shoe factory to produce 30 different models of children's shoes, men's and women's shoes. Knitting and both Garment factories used imported raw materials for 80% of their production in the past years.

In 1994, more than 70 percent of the products were produced on the basis of local raw materials, i.e. localized. As a result, the types of products manufactured at these enterprises have exceeded 250 types. "Nigora" and Bori Amonova sewing factories also produced 150 types of products based on local raw materials.

In 1994, the regional industry was fully privatized, and within eleven months, nearly 2.5 billion soums worth of consumer goods were produced. It was 110 percent compared to the plan.

The volume of production in regional bakery enterprises during eleven months was 116 percent compared to 1992. In 1993, equipment for the production of products based on Swiss technology was installed in the Bukhara bakery. This made it possible to produce high-quality and abundant products. However, the decline in production rates in the regional electric networks, construction materials industry, food and cotton industries had a negative impact on the gross indicators.

It should also be said that in 2 months of 1992, 29 of the existing 90 industrial enterprises did not reach the indicators of the previous year. As a result, about 2 billion soums worth of products were produced less.

At the regular meeting of the Bukhara regional government from December 29, 1993, it was made urgent to organize the work in the labor unions, drastically reduce the number of loss-making enterprises, make the product affordable and provide the market with a wide range of consumer goods.

At the meeting, the results of the 12th session of the Bukhara Regional Council showed the need to pay special attention to social protection measures to stabilize the consumer market and meet the needs of the population as much as possible.

Attention was drawn to the need to expand economic cooperation with the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States. The mutual cooperation agreement concluded between Bukhara region and Kharkiv region of Ukraine is the prospect of establishing strong relations in the field of product exchange, industry and agriculture, and its great importance has been shown by means of vivid evidence and examples.

If we think about the territory and demographic trend of Bukhara region based on the above information: The area of Bukhara region is 40.32 thousand km². The population is more than 1637.1 thousand people (2010). As of January 1, 2011, there are 11 rural districts subordinate to the region: Bukhara (1.32 thousand km²), Vopkent (0.29 thousand km²), Jondor (5.17 thousand km²), Kogon (0.50 thousand km²), Olot (3.22 thousand km²), Peshko' (8.72 thousand km²), Romitan (1.30 thousand km²), Shafirkon (3.72 thousand km²), Karakol (9.84 thousand km²), Qarovulbazar (2.20 thousand km²), Gijduvan districts (3.94 thousand km²). Also, there were 11 cities subordinate to the district, 62 urban-type settlements, and 120 rural citizens' assemblies.

In 1995, the working-age population living in Bukhara region was 682.7 thousand people, of which the economically active population was 555.0 thousand people. 554,200 people were employed in the economy, and 0.8000 people were unemployed with official unemployment status in the labor authorities.

In 1995, if we compare the working population of the region with the employed population of the same year, the number of unemployed people who are not on the list was 127,700 people. Some of these people went to foreign countries (Russia, USA, Korea, China) and joined the cathedral of seasonal workers.

In 1995, 554.2 thousand people were employed in the region: In industry (51.6 thousand), (291.0 in agriculture and forestry), (20.4 in transport and communication), (33.5 in construction), (44.5 in trade, generalization, material and technical supply, trade and preparation), (9.9 in the provision of household services of the household and communal economy, production type to the population), (29.9 in health care, physical education and social welfare), (57.6 in education, culture, art, science and scientific service provision), (2.0 in finance, credit and insurance offices) and other sectors, it can be seen that 13.8 thousand people are permanently employed in these enterprise organizations. 15 years later, according to 2010, the number of people in working capacity was 1024.2 thousand, of which 810.0 thousand were economically active, 768.1 thousand were employed in the economy, and 0.5 thousand were unemployed who received official unemployment status in the labor authorities. In 2010, if we compare the number of economically active population with the number of working people in the region, the number of unemployed people in 2010 was 214,200. These people went to work in foreign countries seasonally, including: Russia, Kazakhstan, the USA, Turkey, Israel and a number of similar countries, without officially applying to regional employment assistance centers. And some workers who went abroad were sent to work in the above Foreign countries after passing the State Register.

In 2010, the indicators of the distribution of the employed population of the population of Bukhara region by economic sector are as follows: (87.1 in industry), (239.6 in agriculture and forestry), (79.9 in transport and communication), (42.1 in construction), (84.6 in trade catering material and technical support, trade and preparation), (18.8 in the provision of housing and communal services, non-

production household services to the population, (57.7 in health care, physical education and social security), (102.7 in the provision of education, culture, art, science and scientific services), (3.6 in finance, credit and insurance agencies) and 52,000 people are employed in other industries.

Analyzing the above data, it can be seen that the permanent employment and economic support of the population living in the region has increased. These indicators show that the region's economy has grown.

Due to the improvement of the social sphere, in 2010, compared to 1995, the number of people who lost their breadwinners decreased by 3.5 thousand people in Bukhara region. Another reason for the decrease in the number of survivors is the increase in the number of medical equipment in 2010, which is fundamentally different from the health care system of 1995, and the increase in the number of private polyclinics and a number of other rural health centers.

To sum up, due to independence, the socio-economic condition of the residents of Bukhara region has been improving year by year, as well as the external relations of Bukhara region have been improving.

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